

Knowledge, Attitude, and Readiness to Practice (KArP) of Healthcare Professionals Toward Disaster Management at Ali-Abad Teaching Hospital (One of the Major Public Hospitals in Afghanistan)

Ali-Abad Eğitim Hastanesindeki Sağlık Çalışanlarının Afet Yönetimine Yönelik Bilgi, Tutum ve Uygulamaya Hazır Olma Durumları (KArP)

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Abstract

Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practice (KArP) level of healthcare staff at Ali Abad teaching hospital in Kabul Afghanistan toward disaster management and preparedness.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted using a self-administered questionnaire in March 2023 with some 107 healthcare staff at Ali-Abad teaching hospital. The chi-square test was used to compare the difference in KArP status between the independent categorical variables. Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis tests were used to compare the participants' scale scores across their socio-demographic characteristics.

Results: Ninety-eight (91.58%) healthcare staff accepted to participate in the study. Only 35.7% of health workers had a good level of knowledge about disaster management and preparedness, 53.1% of healthcare personnel had a positive attitude toward disaster management and preparedness, and nearly 54.1% of health workers scored moderate on the Readiness to Practice scale. Medical doctors, healthcare staff with longer work experience, and those with a history of exposure to disasters had significantly higher KArP scores than their comparative groups.

Conclusion: A moderate level of attitude among respondents is a good opportunity to adopt our educational policies to increase the level of knowledge and Readiness to Practice among health workers in Afghanistan.

Keywords: Disaster, Healthcare personnel, Afghanistan, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice.

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Öz

Amaç: Bu çalışmanın amacı, Kabil Afganistan'daki Ali Abad eğitim hastanesinde çalışan sağlık personelinin afet yönetimi ve afete hazırlık konusundaki Bilgi, Tutum ve Uygulamaya Hazır olma (KArP) düzeylerini değerlendirmektir.

Gereç ve yöntem: Kesitsel bir çalışma, Mart 2023'te Ali-Abad eğitim hastanesindeki 107 sağlık personeli ile kendi kendine uygulanan bir anket kullanılarak gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bağımsız kategorik değişkenler arasındaki KArP durumu farkını karşılaştırmak için ki-kare testi kullanılmıştır. Katılımcıların ölçek puanlarını sosyo-demografik özelliklerine göre karşılaştırmak için Mann-Whitney U ve Kruskal-Wallis testleri kullanılmıştır.

Bulgular: Doksan sekiz (%91,58) sağlık personeli çalışmaya katılmayı kabul etmiştir. Sağlık çalışanlarının yalnızca %35,7'si afet yönetimi ve hazırlık konusunda iyi düzeyde bilgiye sahipken, sağlık personelinin %53,1'i afet yönetimi ve hazırlık konusunda olumlu bir tutuma sahiptir ve sağlık çalışanlarının yaklaşık %54,1'i Uygulamaya Hazırlık ölçeğinde orta düzeyde puan almıştır. Tıp doktorları, daha uzun iş deneyimine sahip sağlık personeli ve afetlere maruz kalma geçmişi olanların KArP puanları, karşılaştırıldıkları gruplara göre önemli ölçüde daha yüksektir.

Sonuç: Katılımcılar arasında orta düzeyde bir tutum olması, Afganistan'daki sağlık çalışanları arasında bilgi düzeyini ve Uygulamaya Hazır Olma Durumunu artırmak için eğitim politikalarımızı benimsemek için iyi bir fırsattır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Afet, Sağlık personeli, Afganistan, Bilgi, Tutum, Davranış.

INTRODUCTION

A disaster can be defined as “any occurrence that causes damage, ecological disruption, loss of human and life or deterioration of health and health services on a scale sufficient to warrant an extraordinary response from outside the affected community or area” (World Health Organization, 1995). Disasters can be caused by natural, man-made, and technological hazards, as well as various factors that influence the exposure and vulnerability of a community (Jha et al., 2013).

According to the Emergency Event Database (EM-DAT), 432 disastrous events related to natural hazards occurred worldwide in 2021. Overall, these accounted for 10,492 deaths, affected 101.8 million people, and caused approximately 252.1 billion US\$ of economic losses. As a continent, Asia was the most severely impacted, suffering 40% of all disaster events and accounting for 49% of the total number of deaths and 66% of the total number of people affected (CRED, 2021).

Afghanistan is highly prone to human-made and natural disasters such as armed conflicts, explosions, earthquakes, floods, flash floods, landslides, and droughts. Afghanistan takes second place after Haiti, in terms of the number of fatalities from natural disasters among low-income countries. The low level of socio-economic development in Afghanistan makes it vulnerable to disasters, resulting in frequent loss of lives, livelihoods,

and public and private property. According to the Disaster Risk Profile of Afghanistan, earthquakes cause 560 fatalities on average per year, over 800,000 people are exposed to floods, droughts cause more than 280 million USD in agriculture damages per year, and 130,000 private buildings are exposed to landslides each year (The World Bank, 2017). But these are just estimations, and only in July 2022 thousands of people lost their lives due to earthquakes, and floods in different provinces of Afghanistan (World Health Organization, 2022).

Health services are the immediate needs in an emergency and healthcare staff play a key role in all phases of disaster management including mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery (World Health Organization & League of Red Cross Societies, 1989). Evacuation and treatment of injuries, control of communicable diseases, provision of Mental Health and Psychosocial Support (MHPSS) services, medical supply, awareness raising, and water, sanitation, and hygiene services are some of the main health needs during a disaster (Ghazanachai et al., 2022; Murphy, 2020; Zahlawi et al., 2019). Therefore, healthcare staff in Afghanistan should be knowledgeable in disaster management and be able to respond effectively to any disaster and emergency crisis.

Studies among healthcare providers in India, Yemen, Pakistan, Ethiopia, and Iran have demonstrated the level of knowledge, attitude, and practices toward disasters ranging from inadequate to somewhat satisfactory (Gillani

et al., 2021; Lalehgani et al., 2018; Naser & Saleem, 2018; Sharma et al., 2016; Sheganew Tassew et al., 2022). During the literature review, I couldn't find any published article on the evaluation of Afghanistan healthcare staff's knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practice (KArP) toward disaster preparedness and management. Thus, this study has evaluated the knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practices of healthcare professionals in Ali-Abad teaching hospital towards disaster management. This study will contribute to providing accurate and trustable evidence about the level of knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practices of healthcare professionals towards disaster management in Afghanistan. Moreover, the results of this study are expected to generate hypotheses for further studies in disaster management. The results of this study are going to be used as a reference or means of justification for training activities for health professionals in disaster management.

METHODOLOGY

Study design: A cross-sectional study was conducted using a self-administered questionnaire in March 2023 at Ali-Abad teaching hospital in Kabul, Afghanistan.

Study setting: The study was conducted in Ali-Abad Teaching Hospital. Ali-Abad Teaching Hospital is one of the biggest and known hospitals in Afghanistan. A total of 397 healthcare professionals (176 medical doctors, 96 nurses, 9 pharmacists, 35 technicians, 22 administrative staff, and 59 other workers) are working in this hospital (KUMS, 2022).

Study population and sampling: The population of the study was all of the healthcare professionals who are actively working in the hospital. The minimum sample size for the study is calculated as 90 participants using the G*Power 3.1.9.2 software. An effect size of 0.3, an alpha error probability of 0.05, and a power of 0.80 are considered during the calculation of sample size. To decrease the chance of error a sample size of 107 participants was used in this study. A stratified random sampling technique was used to select the study participants. In this sampling method, all healthcare staff in the hospital were divided into 3 strata (Medical Doctors, Nurses and technicians, and Administrative staff). Those who were not willing to participate in the study and those who were absent due to annual leave, sick leave, or maternal leave were excluded from the study accordingly.

Data collection: The data collection for the study was carried out using a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed after reviewing related studies done in other developing countries and consultation with related departments at the Kabul University of Medical Sciences (KUMS). The questionnaire was in Dari and included 4 major parts. The first part consisted of socio-demographic questions such as age, gender, profession, department, years of work experience, and exposure to an emergency or disaster. The second, third, and fourth parts included questions to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and Readiness to Practices of the study participants towards disaster management respectively. The data collection form was checked by the related university professor before finalization. The questionnaire was tested in a pilot study of 20 participants to ensure that there is no problem with the design or contents of the questionnaire. The validity of the tool was tested by the calculation of Cronbach's alpha values for Knowledge, Attitude, and Readiness to Practice questions.

Two volunteer medical students (one male and one female) with the supervision and support of the researcher distributed/shared the questionnaires to the study participants. These volunteers received an orientation on the study before the beginning of the data collection process. The questionnaires were checked by the researcher for any possible errors and got an anonymous ID on the cover of the questionnaire.

Data Analysis: Data entry and analysis were done by IBM SPSS Statistics 25. The data was summarized through descriptive statistics and demonstrated in tables and graphics. The questions in the knowledge section were recoded as 1 and 0 for correct and wrong answers and categorized as poor, medium, and high knowledge. There were some eight questions in the knowledge section, the total score was calculated by summing the individual scores for each question giving a theoretical minimum score of zero and a maximum score of eight. The questions in the Attitude and Readiness to Practice sections were in the 3-point Likert Scale form. There were seven questions to evaluate the attitude of participants and six questions to evaluate their readiness to practice toward disaster management. The total score for the attitude section was also calculated by summing the scores for each question (1 for positive attitude and 0 for negative attitude or neutral answer) giving a theoretical minimum score of zero and a maximum score of seven for this section. The same technique was

used for calculating the total scores of the readiness to practice section giving a theoretical minimum score of zero and a maximum score of six for this section. The chi-square test was used to compare the difference in knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practice status between the independent categorical variables. Some of the categorical variables such as age, profession, and department were regrouped during the data analysis phase due to the low number of responses and to maintain the quality of the statistical test results. During the chi-square tests, the categorical outputs of the knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practice scales were regrouped as dichotomous variables to increase the validity of the test. The normality of the respondents' scores in the knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practice skill was examined using the Shapiro-Wilks test, the observation of Q-Q plot, skewness-kurtosis values, and the Mann-Whitney U test and Kruskal-Wallis one-way analysis of variance were used to compare the participants' scale scores across their socio-demographic characteristics accordingly. P-values of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The study's Independent variables were the socio-demographic and other variables which were listed under the first section of the questionnaire, the dependent variables were knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practice of health professionals toward disaster management.

Ethical considerations: The permission of the ethical committee of Kabul University of Medical Sciences and the informed consent of the study participants were obtained accordingly. However, no personal information that reveals their identity was collected during data collection.

FINDINGS

Socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants: The questionnaire was shared with 107 healthcare staff in Ali Abad Hospital, of which 98 (91.58%) were accepted to participate in the study. The socio-demographic characteristics of participants are presented in Table 1. The study sample comprised 55.1% Medical Doctors, 16.3% Nurses, and 28.6% Technicians and Administrative staff, and most of them were male (72.4%). Nearly 46% of the study participants had been working in the hospital for more than 5 years and more than 70% of the participants stated that they had previous exposure to disasters.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of participants (n=98)

Variables	n (%)
Gender	
Male	71 (72.4)
Female	27 (27.6)
Age	
18 – 25 years	25 (25.5)
26 – 35 years	45 (45.9)
36 - 45	23 (23.5)
45+	5 (5.1)
Profession	
Medical Doctor	54 (55.1)
Nurse	16 (16.3)
Technician	14 (14.3)
Administrative Staff	14 (14.3)
Department	
Emergency Department	15 (15.3)
Internal Medicine	23 (23.5)
Surgery	15 (15.3)
Allied Health	26 (26.5)
Administrative	19 (19.4)
Work Experience	
Less than one year	6 (6.1)
1-3 years	27 (27.6)
3-5 years	20 (20.4)
More than 5 years	45 (45.9)
Previous Exposure to Disaster	
Yes	69 (70.4)
No	29 (29.6)

Knowledge, Attitude, and Readiness to Practice of hospital staff regarding disaster management: The internal consistency coefficient Cronbach alpha values are calculated as 0.74 for knowledge, 0.72 for attitude, and 0.62 for Readiness to Practice. The categorical results of the scales are illustrated in Table 2, only 35.7% of health workers in Ali Abad Hospital had a good level of knowledge about disaster management and preparedness. The results showed that 53.1% of healthcare workers evaluated had a positive attitude

towards disaster management and preparedness. Almost, 54.1% of health workers scored moderate/fair on the Readiness to Practice scale regarding disaster management and preparedness, and unfortunately, 41.8% of the study participants had poor Readiness to Practice scores.

Nearly, 96% of the study participants knew what a disaster is, and 73.5% knew the concept of a disaster plan whereas 49% were aware of disaster preparedness plans in their organization. Nearly 86.7% knew what to do in case of an emergency or disaster and only 60.2% were aware of information sources in disaster management and preparedness (Table 3).

Almost 89.8% indicated that they would be interested in educational classes on disaster management and 82.7% agreed that they are willing to be a member of a healthcare response team in a disaster situation. Only 60.2% agreed that they have personnel or family emergency plans (Table 4).

In the Readiness to Practice section, 64.3% of participants stated that they have participated in disaster response interventions in the past whereas, 52.0% mentioned that they have not studied anything about disaster management and preparedness during their educational journey. Similarly, 87.8% agreed that they are willing to attend a disaster management and preparedness training session (Table 5).

Table 2. Categorical results of the study participants' Knowledge, Attitude, and Readiness to Practice disaster management and preparedness (n=98)

Variables	n (%)
Knowledge	
Poor	30 (30.6)
Moderate	33 (33.7)
Good	35 (35.7)
Attitude	
Poor	26 (26.5)
Moderate	52 (53.1)
Good	20 (20.4)
Readiness to Practice	
Poor	41 (41.8)
Moderate	53 (54.1)
Good	4 (4.1)

Table 3. Frequency of participants' answers regarding the Knowledge questions (n=98)

Questions	Yes, n (%)	No n (%)
I know what a disaster is.	94 (95.9)	4 (4.1)
I know what a disaster plan is.	72 (73.5)	26 (26.5)
I know what disaster preparedness is.	81 (82.7)	17 (17.3)
Healthcare staff is responsible for the health aspects of disaster management interventions.	92 (93.9)	6 (6.1)
My organization has a disaster preparedness plan.	48 (49.0)	50 (51.0)
I know what to do in case of an emergency or disaster.	85 (86.7)	13 (13.3)
I am aware of the potential risks of emergencies and disasters in Afghanistan.	84 (85.7)	14 (14.3)
I know where to find necessary information about disaster management and preparedness.	59 (60.2)	39 (39.8)

Table 4. Frequency of participants' answers regarding the Attitude questions (n=98)

Questions	Agree, n (%)	Neither Agree nor Disagree, n (%)	Disagree, n (%)
I consider myself prepared for disaster management.	70 (71.4)	16 (16.3)	12 (12.2)
I would feel confident in my abilities as a healthcare personnel in disaster management.	75 (76.5)	12 (12.2)	11 (11.2)
I would be interested in educational classes on disaster management.	88 (89.8)	2 (2.0)	8 (8.2)
I have personnel/family emergency plans.	59 (60.2)	14 (14.3)	25 (25.5)
I would be willing to be a member of a healthcare response team in a disaster situation.	81 (82.7)	9 (9.2)	8 (8.2)
I do not need any further knowledge/training in disaster management.	38 (38.8)	2 (2.0)	58 (59.2)
I would feel confident in implementing emergency and disaster management plans and procedures.	78 (79.6)	8 (8.2)	12 (12.2)

Table 5. Frequency of participants' answers regarding the Readiness to Practice questions (n=98)

Questions	Agree, n (%)	Neither Agree nor Disagree, n (%)	Disagree, n (%)
I have participated in disaster response intervention in the past.	63 (64.3)	7 (7.1)	28 (28.6)
My role in disaster management is clear.	66 (67.3)	12 (12.2)	20 (20.4)
I am not ready to handle whatever potential risks of emergencies exist in the community.	38 (38.8)	10 (10.2)	50 (51.0)
I am willing to attend a disaster management and preparedness training session.	86 (87.8)	5 (5.1)	7 (7.1)
I have attended workshops/seminars about disaster management and it is enough for me to Readiness to Practice in a real situation.	32 (32.7)	5 (5.1)	61 (62.2)
I have not studied anything about disaster management and preparedness during my educational journey.	51 (52.0)	5 (5.1)	42 (42.9)

The comparison of knowledge scale scores and their categorical outcomes according to the socio-demographic characteristics of participants: The analysis of scores obtained in the knowledge section of the study tool by the socio-demographic categories of health workers revealed that male healthcare workers have a significantly higher mean rank of 54.79 than female healthcare workers. According to the profession, medical doctors had a significantly higher mean rank of 56.93 than the technicians and administrative staff. The mean rank of those who had an experience of more than 5 years of working in the hospital was also significantly higher than those who worked for 3-5 years in Ali Abad Hospital. Finally, the healthcare workers who had previous experience of exposure to a disaster had also a significantly higher mean rank than those who were not exposed to any disastrous event yet (Table 6).

However, in the comparison of categorical outcomes of the Knowledge scale across the socio-demographic characteristics of study participants, statistically significant differences were found only among the medical doctors and technicians (X^2 8.668, P-value 0.034) and those who had a history of exposure to disaster vs those who have not experienced any disaster event in the past (X^2 7.078, P-value 0.008) (Table 7).

Table 6. The comparison of the Knowledge scale scores across the participants' socio-demographic characteristics (n=98)

Variables	Mean Rank	X ² /z	P Value
Gender		-3.078	0.002
Male	54.79		
Female	35.59		
Age		2.631	0.268
18 – 25 years	43.60		
26 – 35 years	48.85		
36+	55.80		
Profession		12.376	0.002^A
Medical Doctor	56.93		
Nurse	50.91		
Technician + Administrative staff	34.38		
Department		1.438	0.487
Emergency Department + Internal Medicine	50.76		
Surgery	50.50		
Technician + Administrative staff	42.52		
Work Experience		10.213	0.006^B
Less than 3 years	43.55		
3-5 years	38.05		
More than 5 years	58.92		
Previous Exposure to Disaster		2.921	0.003
Yes	54.78		
No	36.95		

A: Technician + Administrative staff < Medical Doctor

B: 3-5 years < More than 5 years

Table 7. Knowledge of the study participants stratified by their socio-demographic characteristics (n=98)

Variables	Knowledge		X ²	P-Value
	Poor	Good		
Gender			3.107	0.078
Male	28 (39.4)	43 (60.6)		
Female	16 (59.3)	11 (40.7)		
Age			0.511	0.775
18 – 25 years	12 (48.0)	13 (52.0)		
26 – 35 years	21 (46.7)	24 (53.3)		
36+	11 (39.3)	17 (60.7)		
Profession			8.668	0.034
Medical Doctor	19 (35.2)	35 (64.8)		
Nurse	8 (50.0)	8 (50.0)		
Technician	11 (78.6)	3 (21.4)		
Administrative Staff	6 (42.9)	8 (57.1)		
Department			1.016	0.907
Emergency Department	7 (46.7)	8 (53.3)		
Internal Medicine	11 (47.8)	12 (52.2)		
Surgery	6 (40.0)	9 (60.0)		
Allied Health	13 (50.0)	13 (50.0)		
Administrative	7 (36.8)	12 (63.2)		
Work Experience			2.997	0.224
Less than 3 years	17 (51.5)	16 (48.5)		
3-5 years	11 (55.0)	9 (45.0)		
More than 5 years	16 (35.6)	29 (64.4)		
Previous Exposure to Disaster			7.078	0.008
Yes	25 (65.5)	44 (34.5)		
No	19 (36.2)	10 (63.8)		

The comparison of Attitude scale scores and their categorical outcomes according to the socio-demographic characteristics of participants: The analysis of scores obtained in the Attitude section of the study tool by the socio-demographic categories of health workers revealed that medical doctors have a significantly higher mean rank of 61.46 than nurses, technicians, and administrative staff. The mean rank of healthcare workers in the surgery department was significantly lower than those in the emergency and internal medicine departments. The mean rank of those who had an experience of more than 5 years of working in the hospital was also significantly higher than those who worked for 3-5 years and less than one 3 years in Ali Abad Hospital. Finally, the healthcare workers

who had previous experience of exposure to the disaster had also a significantly higher mean rank than those who were not exposed to any disastrous event yet (Table 8).

Similarly, in the comparison of categorical outcomes of the Attitude scale across the socio-demographic characteristics of study participants, statistically significant differences were found among the medical doctors, technicians, and administrative staff (X² 19.733, P-value <0.001), those who had a history of exposure to disaster vs those have not experienced any disaster event in the past (X² 6.792, P-value 0.009), and between health workers who had an experience fewer than 3 years and those who worked for more than 5 years in Ali Abad hospital (X² 9.180, P-value 0.010) (Table 9).

Table 8. The comparison of the Attitude scale scores within the participants' socio-demographic characteristics (n=98)

Variables	Mean Rank	X ² /z	P-Value
Gender		-1.208	0.227
Male	51.54		
Female	44.15		
Age		0.340	0.844
18 – 25 years	47.36		
26 – 35 years	49.33		
36+	51.67		
Profession		26.186	<0.001^A
Medical Doctor	61.46		
Nurse	43.83		
Technician + Administrative staff	29.79		
Department		7.276	0.026^B
Emergency Department + Internal Medicine	46.45		
Surgery	38.35		
Technician + Administrative staff	31.56		
Work Experience		9.267	0.010^C
Less than 3 years	42.91		
3-5 years	40.20		
More than 5 years	58.47		
Previous Exposure to Disaster		2.381	0.017
Yes	53.72		
No	39.47		

A: Technician + Administrative staff < Medical Doctor, Nurse < Medical Doctor

B: Surgery < Emergency Department + Internal Medicine

C: 3-5 years < More than 5 years, Less than 3 years < More than 5 years

Table 9. The attitude of the study participants stratified by their socio-demographic characteristics (n=98)

Variables	Attitude		X ²	P-Value
	Negative	Positive		
Gender			0.410	0.522
Male	24 (33.8)	47 (66.2)		
Female	11 (40.7)	16 (59.3)		
Age			0.234	0.890
18 – 25 years	8 (32.0)	17 (68.0)		
26 – 35 years	17 (37.8)	28 (62.2)		
36+	10 (35.7)	18 (64.3)		
Profession			19.733	<0.001
Medical Doctor	10 (18.5)	44 (81.5)		
Nurse	6 (37.5)	10 (62.5)		
Technician	10 (71.4)	4 (28.6)		
Administrative Staff	9 (64.3)	5 (35.7)		
Department			57.9	0.584
Emergency Department	3 (20.0)	12 (80.0)		
Internal Medicine	7 (30.4)	16 (69.6)		
Surgery	6 (40.0)	9 (60.0)		
Allied Health	11 (42.3)	15 (57.7)		
Administrative	8 (42.1)	11 (57.9)		
Work Experience			9.180	0.010
Less than 3 years	17 (51.5)	16 (48.5)		
3-5 years	9 (45.0)	11 (55.0)		
More than 5 years	9 (20.0)	36 (80.0)		
Previous Exposure to Disaster			6.792	0.009
Yes	19 (27.5)	50 (72.5)		
No	16 (55.2)	13 (44.8)		

The comparison of Readiness to Practice scale scores and their categorical outcomes according to the socio-demographic characteristics of participants: The analysis of scores obtained in the Readiness to Practice section of the study tool by the socio-demographic categories of health workers revealed that male healthcare workers have a significantly higher mean rank of 53.38 than female healthcare workers. The results showed that healthcare workers aged 36 and above had significantly higher scores on the Readiness to Practice scale than those aged between 18 and 25 years. The mean rank of those who had an experience of more than 5 years of working in

the hospital was also significantly higher than those who worked for 3-5 years and those less than 3 years in Ali Abad Hospital. Finally, the healthcare workers who had previous experience of exposure to the disaster had also a significantly higher mean rank than those who were not exposed to any disastrous event yet (Table 10).

The comparison of categorical outcomes of the Readiness to Practice scale across the socio-demographic characteristics of study participants only revealed statistically significant differences among the healthcare workers who worked less than 3 years and those who worked more than 5 years in Ali Abad hospital (X² 17.384, P-value <0.001) and those who had a history of exposure to disaster vs those who have not experienced any disaster event in the past (X² 5.016, P-value <0.001) (Table 11).

Table 10. The comparison of the Readiness to Practice scale scores within the participants' socio-demographic characteristics (n=98)

Variables	Mean Rank	X ² /z	P-Value
Gender		-2.243	0.025
Male	53.38		
Female	39.30		
Age		6.189	0.045^A
18 – 25 years	40.72		
26 – 35 years	48.19		
36+	59.45		
Profession		5.289	0.071
Medical Doctor	55.04		
Nurse	46.66		
Technician + Administrative staff	40.45		
Department		3.488	0.175
Emergency Department + Internal Medicine	50.49		
Surgery	56.27		
Technician + Administrative staff	40.75		
Work Experience		17.384	<0.001^B
Less than 3 years	37.77		
3-5 years	40.38		
More than 5 years	62.16		
Previous Exposure to Disaster		5.016	<0.001
Yes	58.62		
No	27.79		

A: 18 – 25 years<36+

B: Less than 3 years< More than 5 years, 3-5 years<More than 5 years

Table 11. The Readiness to Practice of the study participants stratified by their socio-demographic characteristics (n=98)

Variables	Readiness to Practice		X ²	P-Value
	Poor	Good		
Gender			0.385	0.535
Male	48 (67.6)	23 (32.4)		
Female	20 (74.1)	7 (25.9)		
Age			4.953	0.084
18 – 25 years	20 (80.0)	5 (20.0)		
26 – 35 years	33 (73.3)	12 (26.7)		
36+	15 (53.6)	13 (46.4)		
Profession			3.913	0.141
Medical Doctor	33 (61.1)	21 (38.9)		
Nurse	13 (81.3)	3 (18.8)		
Technician + Administrative staff	22 (78.6)	6 (21.4)		
Department			2.204	0.332
Emergency Department + Internal Medicine	26 (68.4)	12 (31.6)		
Surgery	9 (60.0)	6 (40.0)		
Technician + Administrative staff	21 (80.8)	5 (19.2)		
Work Experience			11.069	0.004
Less than 3 years	29 (87.9)	4 (12.1)		
3-5 years	15 (75.0)	5 (25.0)		
More than 5 years	24 (53.3)	21 (46.7)		
Previous Exposure to Disaster			18.171	<0.001
Yes	29 (100.0)	0 (0.0)		
No	39 (56.5)	30 (43.5)		

DISCUSSION

Healthcare staff plays a key role in risk mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery of disasters and emergencies (World Health Organization & League of Red Cross Societies, 1989). The importance of the preparedness of healthcare staff towards management

in Afghanistan is further increased considering the high vulnerability to natural disasters and armed conflicts in this country (The World Bank, 2017).

The present study aimed to explore the current knowledge, attitude, and Readiness to Practice attributes towards disaster management and preparedness among healthcare workers in Afghanistan. The findings of this study indicated that the knowledge of healthcare professionals in Ali Abad Hospital was insufficient and needed improvement. The attitude of healthcare workers was moderately positive but there is still a place for improvement. Most of the study participants expressed a positive attitude towards attending training sessions on disaster management and preparedness which is a good opportunity for initiating capacity-building programs which consequently lead to enhancing readiness to Readiness to Practice. Though more than half of the study participants indicated good Readiness to Practice towards disaster management there is still room for improvement. This result was similar to that of studies conducted in Yemen, Ethiopia, Iran, and Pakistan (Gillani et al., 2021; Lalehgani et al., 2018; Naser & Saleem, 2018; Sheganew Tassew et al., 2022).

The study found that male healthcare workers scored significantly higher than female healthcare workers in the knowledge section which is similar to a study conducted in Pakistan (Gillani et al., 2021). According to the profession of study participants, medical doctors had a significantly higher score than the technicians and administrative staff which is in line with the studies conducted among Yemeni, Pakistani, and Iranian healthcare staff where the physicians expressed high levels of knowledge than other healthcare workers (Lalehgani et al., 2017; Naser & Saleem, 2018; Schmidt et al., 2019). Additionally, healthcare personnel with long experience working and those who had previous experience of exposure to a disaster had also a significantly higher score than those with shorter work experience in the health sector and those who were not exposed to any disastrous event in the past. These findings are also similar across studies conducted in other countries indicating that work experience and history of exposure to emergencies are common determinants of better knowledge of disaster management and preparedness (Gillani et al., 2021; Lalehgani et al., 2017; Schmidt et al., 2019). However, one study conducted among Yemeni healthcare professionals indicated that there is no significant difference in the knowledge of healthcare staff based on their professional experience (Naser & Saleem, 2018). Based on these

findings, capacity-building interventions could be more focused on female healthcare staff, new graduates, allied healthcare workers, and administrative staff.

The findings also elicited that the level of attitude regarding disaster management and preparedness among the health professions was statistically different. Medical doctors appeared higher in attitude than nurses, technicians, and administrative staff. This finding is supported by studies conducted among health workers in neighboring countries such as Iran, India, and Pakistan (Gillani et al., 2021; Lalehgani et al., 2017; Sharma et al., 2016). Healthcare workers with more than 5 years of experience and those who had a history of exposure to disaster and emergencies had also higher attitudes toward disaster management and preparedness than their comparative groups. Most of the study participants indicated that would be willing to be a member of a healthcare response team in a disaster situation which is good evidence for the demand to learn and Readiness to Practice disaster management among healthcare staff in Ali Abad Hospital.

The readiness to Practice level of our respondents was moderate to good in line with similar studies conducted in Pakistan, Iran, Ethiopia, India, and Yemen (Gillani et al., 2021; Lalehgani et al., 2017; Naser & Saleem, 2018; Sharma et al., 2016; Sheganew Tassew et al., 2022). Again, the staff's working experience and history of exposure to the disaster were significantly associated with high scores in the Readiness to Practice section.

Acquiring knowledge is an effective way to prevent disasters or to reduce its effects. According to a comprehensive review article on the importance of education on disasters and emergencies, disaster education is a functional, operational, and cost-effective risk management and mitigation tool (Torani et al., 2019). Planning and designing educational programs are necessary for people to respond to disasters. The integration of the medical and health aspects of disaster management and preparedness in health and medical universities and higher education institutions is crucial. Education and training can and will increase awareness regarding the causes, risks, and implications of disasters on financial, social, economic, environmental, and humanitarian aspects. Considering the educational context in Afghanistan, there are remarkable concerns about a significant lack of emphasis on disaster preparedness in the educational curriculum of medical and paramedical students in the country and the demand for wider inclusion of disaster training to improve the willingness to work among healthcare students.

Limitations: The generalizability of findings has taken in the author's concern. The study is conducted in Afghanistan and the results are related to the culture, environment, educational, and professional context of this country which may not be generalized to other countries. Furthermore, the study is conducted among healthcare staff in Ali Abad Hospital which is a teaching hospital in the capital of Afghanistan, thus the results cannot be completely generalized for all healthcare workers in the country. In addition, because the study relied on self-reported data, self-perception may have caused biases.

Conclusion: In precise, the study revealed that the healthcare staff in our study had an insufficient level of knowledge, moderate attitude level, and moderate to high readiness to Readiness to Practice level toward disaster management and preparedness. A moderate level of attitude among respondents is a good opportunity to adopt our educational policies to increase the level of knowledge and Readiness to Practice among health workers in Afghanistan.

REFERENCES

1. CRED. (2021). *2021 Disasters in numbers*. <https://doi.org/10.1787/eee82e6e-en>
2. Ghazanchaei, E., Khorasani-Zavareh, D., Aghazadeh-Attari, J., & Mohebbi, I. (2022). Establishing the Status of Patients With Non-Communicable Diseases in Disaster: A Systematic Review. *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness*, 16(2), 783–790. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dmp.2020.364>
3. Gillani, A. H., Li, S., Akbar, J., Omer, S., Fatima, B., Ibrahim, M. I. M., & Fang, Y. (2021). How Prepared Are the Health Care Professionals for Disaster Medicine Management? An Insight from Pakistan. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19010200>
4. Jha, A. K., Miner, T. W., & Stanton-Geddes, Z. (2013). Appendix A. Disaster Definitions and Classifications. In *Building Urban Resilience* (pp. 167–171). The World Bank. https://doi.org/doi:10.1596/9780821388655_App-A
5. KUMS. (2022). *Ali Abad Hospital | KUMS*. <https://kums.edu.af/en/ali-abad-hospital>
6. Lalehgani, H., Yadollahi, S., Fadaee, Y., Ansari, F., & Karimifard, M. (2017). ناراحتی تیریدم زا میانسراسر امیب شیپ سیناژروا لنسورپ یهاگآ نازیم. (ارحصا ملاقم-5(1 SE)، نارایا سیناژروا ببط ملجم ijem.v2i1.17470 <https://doi.org/10.22037/ijem.v2i1.17470>
7. Lalehgani, H., Yadollahi, S., Fadaee, Y., Ansari, F., & Karimifard, M. (2018). Knowledge of emergency medical service staff on crisis management. *Iranian Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 5(3), e3. <http://journals.sbm.ac.ir/.../13535>
8. Murphy, R. J. (2020). Communicable diseases in humanitarian operations and disasters. *BMJ Military Health*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjilitary-2020-001415>

9. Naser, W. N., & Saleem, H. B. (2018). Emergency and disaster management training; knowledge and attitude of Yemeni health professionals- a cross-sectional study. *BMC Emergency Medicine*, 18(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12873-018-0174-5>
10. Schmidt, M., Schmidt, S. A. J., Adelborg, K., Sundbøll, J., Laugesen, K., Ehrenstein, V., & Sørensen, H. T. (2019). The Danish health care system and epidemiological research: From health care contacts to database records. In *Clinical Epidemiology* (Vol. 11, pp. 563–591). Dove Medical Press Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.2147/CLEPS179083>
11. Sharma, S., Koushal, V., & Pandey, N. (2016). Are our hospitals prepared for disasters? Evaluation of health-care staff vis-à-vis disaster management at a public hospital in India. *International Journal of Health System and Disaster Management*, 4(2), 63. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2347-9019.183231>
12. Sheganew Tassew, F., Ermias Chanie, S., Tekalign Birle, A., Abraham Amare, T., Gashaw, K., Tadila Nega, D., Yeshiambaw Ayenew, E., Dejen, G., Gebrie Yirga, K., Endalkachew Yegizaw, S., & Dejen Feleke, G. (2022). Knowledge, attitude, and practice of health professionals working in emergency units towards disaster and emergency preparedness in South Gondar Zone hospitals, Ethiopia, 2020. *PAMJ*, 41(314). <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2022.41.314.32359>
13. The World Bank. (2017). *Afghanistan disaster risk profile*. The World Bank. https://www.gfdr.org/sites/default/files/afghanistan_low_FINAL.pdf
14. Torani, S., Majd, P. M., Maroufi, S. S., & Dowlati, M. (2019). *The importance of education on disasters and emergencies : A review article*. 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp>
15. World Health Organization. (1995). *Coping with major emergencies : WHO strategy and approach to humanitarian action*. World Health Organization. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/61335>
16. World Health Organization. (2022). *Afghanistan Earthquake in Paktika and Khost-Situation Report* (Vol. 10, Issue 10). https://reliefweb.int/attachments/99330417-df84-4397-86e5-5193069f61a0/WHO_HCC_Sitrep%2310_Earthquake_AFG_17JUL2022.pdf
17. World Health Organization & League of Red Cross Societies. (1989). *Coping with natural disasters : the role of local health personnel and the community*. World Health Organization. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/39422>
18. Zhlawi, T., Roome, A. B., Chan, C. W., Campbell, J. J., Tosiro, B., Malanga, M., Tagaro, M., Obed, J., Iaruel, J., Taleo, G., Tarivonda, L., Olszowy, K. M., & Dancause, K. N. (2019). Psychosocial support during displacement due to a natural disaster: relationships with distress in a lower-middle income country. *International Health*, 11(6), 472–479. <https://doi.org/10.1093/inthealth/ihy099>